

REVEALING LAND CONTROL DYNAMICS IN EMERGING AGRICULTURAL FRONTIERS ¹

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Abstract

The expansion of commodity agriculture into tropical and subtropical woodlands degrades ecosystem functionality, biodiversity, and the livelihood base of millions of people. Understanding where and how agricultural frontiers emerge is thus important. Yet, existing monitoring approaches typically focus on mapping deforestation and do not capture the shifts in land access and ownership that lay the ground for agricultural expansion, thereby missing early stages of frontier development. We develop an approach that captures these early dynamics and apply it to the entire 1,1 million km² of the Chaco, a global deforestation hotspot. Through the detection of linear features indicative of land claims and the analysis of their spatial–temporal dynamics, we reveal that the footprint of agricultural frontiers in the region extends far beyond that of deforestation. Most of the Chaco shows signs of land claiming, and although claiming activity is especially concentrated close to active deforestation, emergent claiming in remote parts of the Bolivian and Paraguayan Chaco indicates rapidly growing interest in land in these regions. Finally, the strong spatial correlation between land claiming and the disappearance of smallholder homesteads points to the social repercussions of early agricultural frontier expansion in the Chaco. By offering a transferable template to map land-control indicators at scale, our approach enables a better understanding of frontier processes and more accurate targeting of policy interventions in emerging agricultural frontiers globally.

Forecasts of the catastrophic social, ecological, and climate outcomes that will likely result from continuing forest loss have led to intensified global efforts to combat deforestation (1–3). Multisectorial initiatives such as the New York Declaration on Forests and the Glasgow Declaration on Forest and Land Use, both of which entail commitment by global leaders to end deforestation by 2030 (4, 5), have been paralleled by a growing number of corporate pledges for deforestation-free supply chains (6, 7). However, despite increasingly widespread commitments from both public and private sectors, tropical forest loss accelerated between 2020 and 2023 (8), and several regions recognized as critical to conservation and climate change mitigation efforts have recently experienced the highest rates of deforestation since the turn of the century (9). While multiple factors contribute to these trends (10–12), the leading driver of global deforestation is the expansion of industrialized agriculture (13), as has been the case for now over four decades (14). Specifically, a handful of commodities (namely beef, oil palm, and soybean) account for a large share of all forest loss related to agriculture (15). The impacts associated with land demand for these commodities affect certain regions more than others (16–18), owing not only to their suitability for agriculture but also often to underlying social conditions of poverty, marginalization, and corruption that allow existing social and ecological systems to be displaced with relative ease (19, 20). The need for stricter restrictions on deforestation is pressing, not least because deforestation disproportionately inflicts harm on the world’s most vulnerable populations (21–23). An understanding of the expansion dynamics of agricultural commodity frontiers into the world’s tropical and subtropical woodlands is therefore essential. To date, the characterization of these dynamics has primarily relied on the detection of deforestation for cropland and pasture (24–26). Yet such data do not capture changes in land control and so overlook the shifts in land access and resource ownership that lay the groundwork for the conversion of forest to agriculture (27, 28). Instead, it captures agricultural expansion at a late stage, when in most cases it is too late to intervene. Our aim was to develop an approach to map land-control changes associated with the early stages of agricultural frontier development—thereby opening the possibility of intervention prior to the occurrence of large-scale deforestation and of the stark social–ecological impacts associated with it.

We demonstrate our approach for the Chaco, a dry tropical and subtropical forest ecoregion extending over 1.1 million km² between Argentina, Bolivia, and Paraguay, as well as a current hotspot of deforestation for commodity agriculture (26, 29, 30). In the region, linear forest demarcations, consisting of narrow strips of cleared forest, are used by different actors to lay claim to the exclusive use of forested land, most often for the eventual conversion to cattle pasture or cropland for soybean cultivation (31–33). These linear demarcations hold legal weight in land titling processes, both as markers of property boundaries and as proofs of the “productive use” of forested land (34–36). We thus leverage demerging forest demarcations as indicators of changes in land control occurring in a region where, traditionally, land has been managed communally or under open access by Indigenous and non-Indigenous smallholders (37, 38). Mapping forest demarcations for the year 2020 and tracking when these demarcations emerged across the Chaco allowed us to assess the distribution and temporal dynamics of land claiming in forested areas, relate land claiming to deforestation, and examine the overlap between claiming pressure and the disappearance of dispersed smallholder home-steads—in short, to assess the dynamics in and impacts associated with the early stages of expansion of commodity frontiers.

1. Results

1.1. Mapping Forest Demarcations.

As opposed to field boundaries and road features (39, 40), forest demarcations have a variable spectral signature, making their detection challenging. Key to overcoming this challenge was the use of Sentinel-2 image morphology analysis to isolate features based on their shape (commonly multiple kilometers in length, and 5 to 25 m in width), paired with supervised machine learning as a way to group disjointed features into meaningful structures (41). Once linear features were detected for 2020 across the region, we isolated forest demarcations by masking irrelevant linear elements such as roads and waterbodies. To examine the temporal dynamics of the mapped demarcations, we extracted the year of appearance of each demarcation segment between 1986 and 2020 using a Landsat image time series (42). Our overall approach thus consisted of four main steps: 1) feature delineation, 2) isolation of demarcations, 3) timing of demarcations, and 4) analysis of frontier dynamics (SI Appendix, Fig. S1). For 2020, we detected over 290,000 km of forest demarcations across the Chaco. A linear correspondence analysis between the demarcations extracted automatically and ones mapped manually indicated a 69% overall dataset completeness (i.e., the coverage achieved by the extraction process) and 86% correctness (i.e., the percentage of extracted features that correspond to a reference feature). Completeness jumped up to 84% on reference features we manually labeled as “certainly” being demarcations (i.e., clear uninterrupted, wide lines), meaning that the method dependably detected forest demarcations made by agribusinesses actors, which tend to be >10 m-wide and are cleared with heavy machinery. We obtained the highest detected accuracy for the Bolivian Dry Chaco, with 91% overall completeness, and the lowest for the Argentine Dry Chaco (overall completeness of 60%, yet with an 85% correctness; SI Appendix, Table S5). Regarding the accuracy of the detected date of appearance, we found the average deviation from the manually dated reference demarcations to be 2 y or less (SI Appendix, Table S6).

1.2. Distribution and Dynamics of Land Claims in the Gran Chaco

To assess the distribution of land claims in the Gran Chaco for the year 2020, we calculated the total length of demarcations in forested areas divided by the total forested area within 10 km grid cells (Materials and Methods and Section 3.3). Mapping this density metric across the Chaco revealed that, of the remaining forested area in 2020 (~66% of the total area), a major portion (30%) had medium to very high levels of land claiming, corresponding to more than ~3 km of demarcations per 100 km² of forest. These areas were mainly located in the northernmost portion of the Bolivian Chaco, in western Paraguay, and in the central and northern Argentine Chaco (Fig. 1 A and B). A large portion (37%) of the remaining woodlands were classified as having very low claiming density (1.5 km or less per 100 km² of forest). Protected areas, though they represented a small share of the forested Chaco (~15%), contained 25% of these very low claiming density areas (SI Appendix, Fig. S19), while also containing very few (2%) grid cells classified as having high to very high claiming density (i.e., more than 5 km of demarcations per 100 km² of forest). Outside protected areas, cells with very low claiming density were largely located in less agriculturally suitable areas (SI Appendix, Fig. S20).

To characterize the temporal dynamics of land claims, we derived three additional metrics for each grid cell: 1) Claiming speed (the SD of the year of demarcation appearance, with a smaller SD indicating a faster speed); 2) Peak period of claiming activity (the mode of demarcation appearance); and 3) Last activity (the most recent year of detection within a grid cell). This revealed that a large share (43%) of the remaining forested region was experiencing active land claiming (last claim appearance dated between 2016 and 2020) and that there were peaks of claiming activity between 2015 and 2020 in north-eastern Argentina, northern Paraguay, and in the north-western Bolivian Chaco (Fig. 1A).

We used combinations of these metrics to define three claiming patterns of interest: consolidation, maintenance, and emergence (Fig. 1C). We then used a density-based cluster analysis to identify “hotspots” of these claiming patterns (SI Appendix, section 4). Areas experiencing claim consolidation, meaning that they presented simultaneously medium to very high claiming density and active claiming, were mostly clustered around agricultural expansion fronts. Particularly evident consolidation clusters were found in central and northern areas of the Argentine Chaco (Fig. 1C, zones c, d, and g), and in the north of the Bolivian Chaco (j). Areas exhibiting claim maintenance had a high density of forest demarcations but no new claims since 2016, meaning that while demarcations in these areas were not cleared recently, they were still visible and therefore likely being at least partially maintained (otherwise, vegetation would have regrown). These were predominantly found in the Argentine Chaco, with clusters in the south (Fig. 1C, e) and in the northwest (i). The latter corresponds to a concentration of survey lines from oil exploration in the 1970s and 80s, many of which were later adopted as property demarcations. Areas with emergent claiming, that is, with low claim density but rapid appearance of new claims, were more dispersed compared to the latter two activity patterns, with loose clustering in the Humid Chaco of Paraguay and Argentina, and along the Bolivia–Paraguay border.

1.3. Comparing Land Claiming to Deforestation-Based Frontier Indicators.

We used the deforestation frontier “activeness” indicator produced by Baumann et al. (25) to assess how land claiming relates spatially to deforestation for cropland and pasture across the Chaco. Examining the distribution of land claims relative to active deforestation fronts (i.e., areas with a high woodland loss rate between 2016 and 2020, relative to 1985 and 2015), we found substantial overlap between the latter and areas of high to very high claiming (Fig. 2). These active deforestation frontiers also intersected strongly with the pattern clusters, particularly claiming consolidation (SI Appendix, Fig. S24). Beyond areas of overlap, claiming density across the Chaco was highest in the immediate vicinity of deforestation. Paraguay had a steeper decrease in claiming density with distance from the active deforestation frontier, likely due to the little contiguous forest left in the region. Areas experiencing fast, active, and recent claiming (peak period 2015-2020) were also found closest to active deforestation fronts on average (see plots in Fig. 2 and SI Appendix, Fig. S25).

1.4. Approximating the Social Impact of Land Claiming

To approximate the potential impact of claiming activity across the Chaco, we used a dataset of points representing dispersed forest smallholder homesteads ($n = 23,954$) for the Chaco and containing information about their temporal dynamics (appearance, persistence, or disappearance between 1985 and 2018) (43). To examine the relationship between these temporal dynamics and land claiming at the point level, we attributed to each homestead the mean values of the claiming metrics in a 10 km circular buffer around it. We then calculated 1) the proportion of homesteads within each grid cell that were present in 1985 but that had disappeared by 2018, 2) the proportion of homesteads that had persisted continuously between 1985 and 2018, and 3) the mean value of claiming metrics within 275 km² grid cells (i.e., aggregation). This allowed us to examine the relationship between land claiming and homestead disappearance/persistence across the Chaco (Fig. 3 and SI Appendix, Figs. S27–S30).

While we did not directly characterize land claims according to the actors staking them, the stark disparities in financial, social, and technological capabilities between agribusiness actors and smallholders in the region (44–46) make it very likely that the former are responsible for

the vast majority of these claims. An external claim can represent a variety of situations for a smallholder family or community, as investors who lay claim to a plot of land may do so with or without enforcing measures to exclude people from occupying or using that land (47, 48). For instance, where families occupy land claimed by outside investors decades prior, they may be temporarily undisturbed despite those claims being maintained, or they may have verbal or contractual agreements (e.g., paying rent to the claimant) for the use of that land. However, where those external actors deem exclusion to be in their interest, old and new claims alike become hard boundaries, the crossing of which can result in violence (31). Demarcations cleared by smallholders themselves, often as a strategy in the face of increasing pressures on access, also have an important part to play in the reconfiguration of land control (49). Specifically, where families individually (rather than collectively) place claims to private use, the pressure to privatize may produce a self-reinforcing cycle of internalized access loss. The loss of communal or open access to resources then presents as a major challenge to the continued reproduction of smallholder livelihoods, particularly in what concerns livestock rearing and timber harvesting activities (50).

The impact of these external and internal pressures was reflected in our results by the considerable overlap we found between areas with high claiming density and those with a high proportion of homestead disappearance (black hexagons in Fig. 3). Notably, areas that had seen a high proportion of homestead disappearance were concentrated in and around the “hotspots” of claiming maintenance, consolidation, and emergence (Fig. 3, a-f). Conversely, we found overlap between areas of low claiming density and those with lower levels of homestead disappearance (gray hexagons in Fig. 3). When mapping homestead persistence, these areas of overlap with low claiming density were further accentuated (SI Appendix, Fig. S28). A preliminary exploration of the probability of disappearance and persistence relative to claiming density using simple logistic regressions supported these visual assessments: As claiming increases in a given area, the likelihood of homesteads disappearing increases while, simultaneously, the likelihood of persistence decreases (Fig. 3 and SI Appendix, Fig. S30 and Table S11).

1.5. Approach Limitations.

Our approach to capture the early dynamics of agricultural commodity frontiers in the Chaco comes with some limitations. First, we detected land claims visible in 2020, and so did not capture land claiming in areas that were deforested for agriculture before 2020. The approach therefore does not permit a full reconstruction of land claiming patterns across the landscape. Second, given the possibility of demarcations being abandoned and disappearing by 2020 due to vegetation regrowth, we may underestimate past claiming intensity in certain areas. Anecdotal evidence and experience in the field suggest claim abandonment to be a very rare occurrence, however, and so the bias produced by such misses should be minimal. Third, it is important to note that a greater deviation from the reference year of detection over the periods of 2000-2007 and 2008-2014 likely skewed the temporal metrics downward. In other words, the claiming dynamics metrics likely underestimate the overall recency of claiming activity (SI Appendix, section 3). Fourth, because timber extraction roads in the Chaco tend to meander and branch, we were able to exclude the vast majority of these by using a Hough Line filter during the feature detection. However, a small portion of the detected demarcations might still correspond to large, straight logging roads (which, as logging roads are not surveyed, would not be included in the road databases we used for masking). This should not affect our results

substantially, as long, straight logging roads are uncommon in the Chaco and such roads would generally run along property boundaries and overlap with municipal roads. In turn, some demarcations could also correspond to energy transmission lines. In the Chaco, these tend to follow surveyed roads, and so the majority will have effectively been masked. Visual assessment of the approach performance in excluding logging roads and energy transmission lines is provided in SI Appendix, Figs. S12 and S13, respectively. Finally, the approach, while reliably detecting larger demarcations cleared with machinery by agribusiness (i.e., 10 to 20 m wide, known locally as “picadas”), less reliably picked up smaller demarcations (3 to 5 m) cleared by hand by smallholders (“deslindes”). The claiming dataset produced, and the results obtained from analyzing it, should therefore be understood as providing a representation of broad-scale land claiming dynamics.

2. Discussion

The continued expansion of agricultural commodity production into the world’s tropical and subtropical forests represents one of the greatest threats to Earth system functioning (51) and adds to the harms affecting the world’s most vulnerable (52). With corporate and governmental accountability still lacking in many regions, monitoring these expanding frontiers of resource appropriation is essential. Specifically, detecting early phases of frontier development allows for a timelier targeting of interventions and enforcement, prior to the occurrence of large-scale deforestation. Yet, for many commodity frontiers, information on land deals, agricultural rents, and deforestation permits is unavailable (53, 54), not uncommonly due to the concealment of official registries and the illegal nature of land acquisitions (55–57).

The growing availability of high-resolution satellite imagery (58) as well as increased data handling capabilities (59) has now opened the door to the detection of proxies for land processes which ground data are unavailable for (60, 61). Here, we made use of these to develop a remote-sensing approach to map land claiming activity occurring in forested areas prospected for agricultural commodity production. We demonstrate the usefulness of this approach for the entire 1,1 million km² of the Chaco, one of the world’s deforestation hotspots (26, 30). In the region, the legal weight of forest demarcations in sustaining claims to land ownership has led to their almost ubiquitous uptake to secure access to land (31–33). This makes these often-disregarded thin deforested strips valuable indicators of changes to resource control happening in forested parts of the Chaco.

2.1. Forests Surrounding Croplands and Pastures Are Heavily Fragmented by Land Claims.

We found that land claiming activity in the Chaco was concentrated in and around deforestation fronts. Across the Argentine, Paraguayan, and Bolivian parts of the region, hotspots of land claiming activity coincided with and extended immediately beyond areas undergoing active expansion of cropland and pasture. This points to how the process of securing control over land plays an instrumental part in propelling agricultural expansion, by laying the groundwork for the contiguous advance of deforestation frontiers observed in the region. Identification of these claiming hotspots serves to highlight possible trajectories in the “contagious” process of frontier expansion (62). For example, clusters of land claiming consolidation in the northern Argentine Chaco indicate a likely eastward expansion from the agricultural nucleus in the province of

Salta; a north- and westward expansion from the Chaco province nucleus, and a capture of most of the remaining forestland in the western part of Formosa province. In Bolivia, consolidation suggests a further expansion of the frontier south and eastward from the main agricultural triangle of the Eastern Lowlands. In Paraguay, where much of the Chaco has already been converted, clusters of consolidation along the Bolivian border points to a likely expansion of cattle ranching into these last remaining areas of unconverted forest.

2.2. Agricultural Frontiers Extend Far beyond Deforestation Fronts.

Our results reveal that land claiming activity is not limited to the areas immediately surrounding active deforestation for agriculture. Rather, claims fragment forested areas that, based on land-use change indicators alone, would be considered largely “untouched” by agricultural activity, indicating that early frontier activity is occurring throughout most of the Chaco. In the Argentine portion of the region, many of these more remote claims were made during the onset and take-off of the commodity boom in the region (1995-2007) and were maintained open until 2020. This suspended state of land claiming across much of the Argentine Chaco is highly concerning, as it hints at a waiting game played by land investors. With the disbandment of environmental and social protections proposed by the Milei government since 2023, the threat of the reactivation of frontiers in these areas is elevated (63, 64).

Beyond the widespread presence of older claims maintained over time, we also observed the rapid appearance of new land claims between 2016 and 2020 across much of the central and northeastern Argentine Chaco—despite some of that territory being protected by the forest law in Argentina (65). Similarly, emergent claiming activity around the triple frontier and along the northern border between Bolivia and Paraguay indicate a relatively recent and growing interest in land in these two countries—a trend on par with the extractivist political and economic agenda seen in both countries in the last decade (66, 67).

Not all of the Chaco has been visibly claimed, however. Our analysis also allowed us to identify areas that were not displaying land claiming activity in 2020. These were concentrated in less agriculturally suitable regions (chiefly arid areas and saline or steep soils), and, importantly, in protected areas, with the boundaries of national parks (such as Copo National Park in Argentina, Kaa-Iya National Park in Bolivia, and Medanos del Chaco National Park in Paraguay) aligning with a sudden drop in land claiming activity compared to the unprotected surroundings. This finding points to the importance of heightened protections and enforcement in safeguarding forests and the people living within them, particularly as agricultural frontiers draw nearer these once remote areas (68–70).

2.3. Smallholder Homestead Disappearance Coincides with Land Claiming Pressures.

The continued expansion of commodity agriculture into tropical and subtropical forests represents a direct threat to the livelihoods of millions of forest-dependent people globally (43). Our study demonstrates that this threat is not limited to areas actively undergoing deforestation. Beyond the deforestation front, families and communities are experiencing the consequences of a race to secure control over land prospected for commodity production (71, 72). This grabbing of control (73) oftentimes begins with land claims made through legal registration (though not necessarily by legal means) and physical “proofs” of merit to ownership—a process

that culminates well before a plot is converted to agriculture with the enforcement of rights to private access (73, 74). The presence of forest thus does not necessarily equate with its accessibility for forest-dependent smallholders and may mask ongoing processes of exclusion.

In exposing the spread of land claiming across the Chaco, our analysis evidences the intense land pressures faced by forest-dwelling smallholders in the region. The spatial correlation between smallholder homestead disappearance and land claiming activity further underscores the gravity of the situation. Indeed, we found that where land claiming activity was highest, so was homestead disappearance, not just in areas undergoing active deforestation but also in more remote, forested areas. Although these results offer only a coarse, preliminary view of the social impacts of land claiming across the region, what they point to is that the delimiting of land signals not only a future threat to smallholder access, to be realized in the moment of deforestation, but also, in many instances, an immediate change in the norms of access to land and resources that has direct consequences for local livelihoods.

2.4. An Urgent Need for the Monitoring of Agricultural Frontiers.

By putting the early dynamics of land claiming for agricultural expansion on the map, our findings reveal a more complete picture of emerging commodity frontiers—a “truer” footprint that goes beyond the land-use conversions occurring at a later stage to encompass changes in land control that give way to them. This complements other ongoing efforts to characterize key but little-visible processes of early frontier development, such as the appearance of ghost roads (75). The pervasiveness of land claiming activity around, but also far beyond, active deforestation fronts in the Chaco likely mirrors processes in other woodland regions seeing the expansion of agricultural frontiers. Forest-focused monitoring of land claiming is thus essential. Without it, we will continue to miss changes in the dynamics of resource access which, ultimately, set the stage for the destruction of forests and the disruption of the lives of the people dependent on them. Our approach offers a template for the mapping of land-control indicators across large geographic extents—also complementing tenure mapping initiatives (76–78). The focus on image morphology, rather than purely on spectral signals, makes our method modulable to differently shaped features and to higher or lower-resolution input imagery. It is thus transferable to different global contexts where the specific land control change indicator will necessarily differ. Additionally, for the Chaco, the approach provides a rapid and dependable way to continue monitoring land claiming in the region going forward.

With the ability to monitor the early expansion dynamics of frontiers comes the possibility of flagging areas at risk of experiencing deforestation, and therefore of enhancing pressures for governmental and corporate accountability. Our approach can therefore serve as a tool for advocacy, to prevent or mitigate the social and ecological harms associated with early agricultural expansion in areas where power asymmetries are often stark, and enforcement of regulation to protect the vulnerable and the environment is low. This shift in how agricultural expansion is understood and monitored—a broadening of lens that suddenly reveals a larger and more complete picture—opens up possibilities for the protection of tropical and subtropical forests and the people reliant upon them.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Mapping the Appearance of Demarcations across the Chaco.

To map demarcations across the Chaco, we used Sentinel-2 Level-2A orthorectified, atmospherically corrected surface reflectance imagery for the dry season in 2020 (79). First, we masked out all clouds and cloud shadows and calculated a set of spectral-temporal metrics (25, 80) at 10 m spatial resolution. We removed any outliers (high and low) in the imagery to increase overall contrast of the linear features within the image. Second, we applied several image morphology operations to generate an initial set of candidate demarcations. To start, we applied a Sato filter to map the probabilities of tubularity (i.e., probability of forming part of a long and hollow image feature) (81), and then isolated the areas of high probability, allowing us to obtain a simplified, binary image of tubular landscape features (output a). Then, in order to isolate highly reliable straight and long features within this binary space, we applied a Hough line transformation (82). By specifying restrictive parameters for this transformation, we obtained an output (b) lacking in completeness but containing a set of high-confidence linear features. Third, we used these high-confidence features to train a Random Forest (RF) classifier (83) to identify all other linear features in our study area while eliminating gaps left in previous steps. To account for land-cover specific variations (e.g., degraded vs. undisturbed woodlands) across the Chaco that impact reflectance, we parameterized individual classifiers for regions of 10×10 km. Fourth, we used image morphology operations to clear the RF model output of small lines which, after visual inspections, appeared to be misclassifications (SI Appendix, Fig. S2).

In order to isolate forest demarcations among the totality of detected linear features across the Chaco, we used existing geospatial datasets (84–88) to mask out features that overlapped roads and highways, urban areas, cropland and pastures, and water bodies (i.e., rivers, lakes, reservoirs, wetlands, and salt flats). To then identify the year of appearance of each forest demarcation, we employed the LandTrendr temporal segmentation (89) using annual median Landsat imagery composites. We applied LandTrendr to each mapped segment and derived the “year of greatest disturbance” as indicator for the year of creation of the demarcation (between 1986 and 2020). Example outputs across different regions are provided in SI Appendix, Figs. S5 and S6.

3.2. Method Validation.

We validated our forest demarcation dataset in two ways. First, we validated the contemporary map of forest demarcations (i.e., whether a demarcation was identified correctly or not for 2020) by using the linear correspondence analysis protocol developed by Wiedmann (90) that has been applied to validate linear feature extraction (namely road data) across a number of studies (91–93). In summary, the protocol involves comparing (i.e., “matching”) the automatically extracted features to reference segments. To produce the reference data for the case at hand, we manually digitized forest demarcations within 130 randomly selected, 10 km² validation hexagons (for a total of $\approx 1,000$ km in length of reference features produced for the Chaco). The accuracy of the automatic extraction method was, following Wiedmann, assessed by calculating two basic correspondence metrics: completeness and correctness. Completeness quantifies the coverage achieved by the extraction process (where a completeness score of 1 (or 100%) indicates perfect extraction coverage, meaning all reference features have been accurately extracted).

Correctness, on the other hand, evaluates the proportion of the extracted features that correctly correspond to the reference data, offering insight into the accuracy of the extraction [where a

correctness score of 1 (or 100%) indicates that all extracted features correspond to the reference data].

We assessed completeness according to both the total matched demarcation references and matched “certain” references (i.e., reference segments we were certain were demarcations), thus providing a two-tier evaluation of coverage (SI Appendix, Figs. S7 and S8 and Table S5). Additionally, we validated the dataset temporally by manually assigning a year of appearance to demarcation segments (evaluated using yearly Landsat imagery composites), and then computing the average deviation in years assigned between the reference and extracted segments (SI Appendix, Figs. S9 and S10 and Table S6). Details on the temporal validation are provided in SI Appendix, section 3.

3.3. Analyzing Demarcation Distribution and Dynamics.

We produced several metrics at 10 km spatial resolution to characterize land claiming distribution and dynamics (Fig. 1A and SI Appendix, Table S7). To characterize claiming distribution, we produced a demarcation density metric, calculated as the sum of demarcation lengths divided by the total forested area within each 10×10 km grid cell. This correction was done so that the metric reflected density specifically within forested areas, without which grid cells with more deforestation would erroneously have been shown as having lower density. We then classified the density values using the Natural Breaks (Jenks) classification algorithm (SI Appendix, Fig. S14). To characterize claiming dynamics, we assessed the peak claiming period, the speed of claiming, and the most recent claiming activity (last activity). For the peak period, we first classified demarcation segments into periods corresponding to stages of the expansion of large-scale agriculture in the region: 1986-1994 corresponds to the period before the take-off of agricultural frontiers in the area, 1995-1999 to the entry of genetically modified soybean in the region, 2000-2007 to the land rush following the Argentine economic crisis, 2008-2014 to the peak of commodity frontier expansion, and finally, 2015-2020 corresponds to the most recent conditions (25, 94–96). We then assigned each grid cell the majority period, by segment count, of demarcation appearance. Speed of claiming activity was defined in terms of the SD of the year of demarcation appearance, with greater SD meaning slower claiming, as they imply that different segments appeared in years further apart than average (SI Appendix, Fig. S15). Last claiming activity was calculated as the most recent year of claiming activity detected within a grid cell, then classified as either 1986-2015 (i.e., inactive) or 2016-2020 (i.e., active). Metric summaries by frontier regions and by province are found in SI Appendix, Figs. S16 and S17 and Tables S8 and S9).

In order to highlight key claiming dynamics in the area, we then used combinations of these metrics to classify a subset of the 10×10 km grid cells into three different claiming patterns: 1) consolidation, 2) maintenance, and 3) emergence. We classified as experiencing “consolidation” the cells that simultaneously had medium to very high claiming density, peak activity between 1986 and 2020, and active claiming, i.e., where new claims were being added to an already high density of claims. Cells experiencing “maintenance” had high to very high claiming density, peak activity between 1986 and 2014, and inactive claiming, i.e., no new claims were being made, but a high density of older claims were maintained open up to 2020. “Emergence” corresponded to very low to low claiming density, peak activity between 2000 and 2020, active claiming, and medium to fast claiming speed, i.e., where there were relatively rapidly accumulating new claims in an area with previously low or no claims (SI Appendix, Table S10). To identify pattern hotspots for discussion, we conducted a density-based cluster analysis on the isolated grid cells (SI Appendix, section 4). Reliable clusters were identified by testing multiple combinations of the search distance and minimum-features-per-cluster

parameters, for each pattern individually and for a combination of the three patterns (SI Appendix, Fig. S18).

3.4. Relating Land Claiming to Deforestation Frontier Indicators.

To relate the claiming metrics to the deforestation activeness measure produced by Baumann et al. for the region (25), we used a 10 km² hexagonal grid, for which each grid cell was assigned claiming metric values at its centroid. To liberally capture the reach of ongoing deforestation, the maximum value that fell within each hexagon was then used to assign each a frontier timing value, i.e., active (=2) trumped suspended (=1), and emerging (=3) trumped active. This resulted in a unified dataset containing both claiming metrics and deforestation activeness values for the region. We then examined the spatial relationship between deforestation activeness and land claiming by calculating the metric distance from each 10 km² hexagon to the nearest hexagon classified as having active deforestation for agriculture, exploring patterns across the region and by country (Fig. 2 and SI Appendix, Figs. S24 and S25).

3.5. Examining the Relationship between Land Claiming and Homestead Dynamics.

To examine the potential social impact of claiming activity across the Chaco, we used forest-smallholder homestead point data (n = 23,954), which contained information on when, between 1985 and 2018, each homestead was visible in Landsat image time series, and thus whether a homestead emerged, disappeared, or was persistent (43). We first extracted mean claiming metric values within 10 km from each homestead. We then produced a large hexagonal grid (275 km²) over which to simultaneously summarize both claiming conditions and smallholder homestead dynamics of disappearance and persistence. Disappearance was calculated as the proportion of homesteads within each grid cell that were present in 1985 but had disappeared by 2018. Persistence, in turn, was calculated as the proportion of homesteads that had continuously been reported as present between 1985 and 2018. With this joint dataset, we then explored the relationship between land claiming and smallholder homestead dynamics via visual interpretation of bivariate choropleths (Fig. 3 and SI Appendix, Fig. S27 for all metric comparisons and SI Appendix, Figs. S28 and S29 for comparisons of disappearance and persistence trends). Using the homestead points, each of which was assigned local metric values as detailed in the first step, we also explored these relationships by means of logistic regressions (SI Appendix, Fig. S30 and Table S11).

Data, Materials, and Software Availability

All analysis scripts of this research are openly available in the following GitHub repository: (https://github.com/odelgi/LandClaiming_analysis) (97). Data (i.e., linear demarcation segments mapped across the Gran Chaco as well as aggregated land claiming metric maps for the entire region) will be stored by the authors (in an institutional repository) and will be available upon reasonable request, meaning showing intent of use to either a. further academic research or b. interest by non-profits and government agencies. This partial restriction has been decided on in order to avoid the data being used as a tool in agricultural suitability analyses.

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Author contributions

O.d.G., M.B., T.K., and Y.I.P.d.W. designed research; O.d.G. performed research; O.d.G. analyzed data; M.B. contributed to the methodology and data curation; T.K. and Y.I.P.d.W. provided resources; and O.d.G. wrote the paper.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interest.

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FIG. 1.

Land claiming dynamics in the Gran Chaco. Maps in panel (A) depict the four claiming metrics across the region. Panel (B) shows the layout of demarcations (in magenta) against the mapped density metric in (clockwise from Top-Left) the northern Bolivian Chaco, the western Paraguayan Chaco, and the central and southern Argentine Chaco. Red Insets within those are used to demonstrate how the extracted forest demarcations map onto the satellite imagery. The larger map on the Right (C) shows the distribution of claiming consolidation (red), maintenance (blue), and emergence (orange) across the Chaco. The specific combinations of metric classes used to classify areas into those three claiming pattern types is detailed below the map. Lettered Insets (a-j) point to pattern clusters.

FIG. 2.

Spatial comparison of land claiming and deforestation for agricultural commodity production across the Chaco. Points in the plots represent the mean class value per country.

FIG. 3.

Exploring the relationship between land claiming and smallholder homestead dynamics. The map relates mean claiming density to the proportion of smallholder homesteads disappeared by 2018 within each hexagonal grid cell. Hexagons containing no homesteads between 1985 and 2018 are not mapped. Letters denote areas (circled) of high homestead disappearance that coincided with hotspots of claiming maintenance, consolidation, and/or emergence. The plot Inset shows the probability of homestead disappearance (dark trend line) and persistence (light trend line) according to the degree of claiming intensity experienced within 10 km of homesteads. Additional details in SI Appendix, section 6.